

IMPACT OF KRUSHI VIGYAN KENDRA ON ADOPTION LEVEL OF POTATO GROWERS ABOUT POTATO PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

A large number of agricultural technologies are available, but full use of it is not being done in many parts of the country. Thus, there is a big gap in the technology generation and dissemination. Looking into these facts, it is necessary to undertake impact assessment study of Krushi Vigyan Kendra. The present study was undertaken in Deesa KVK of Banaskantha district. Out of 14 talukas of Banaskantha District seven talukas falls under the jurisdiction of KVK Banaskantha-I(Deesa). Among the seven talukas four taluka and from each selected talukas three villages were selected purposively. From the list of KVK beneficiary, ten beneficiary and ten non beneficiary potato growers from each village were selected randomly. Thus, altogether 120 beneficiary and 120 non beneficiary potato growers were selected. Ex-post facto research design was used for this study. 'Z' test was applied to determine the difference between KVK beneficiary and non beneficiary potato growers. Results of the investigating showed that majority (79.17%) of beneficiary farmers had medium to high level and (86.67%) of non beneficiary farmers had low to medium level of adoption of potato production technology.

Key Words: Impact, Adoption, Potato Production Technology, Beneficiary and Non beneficiary farmers

Introduction

Krushi Vigyan Kendra, an innovative science-based institution, was consequently established mainly to impart vocational training to the farmers and field level extension workers. The concept of vocational training in agriculture through KVK grows substantially due to greater demand for improved agricultural technology by the farmers. They act as the training centers for the transfer of technology with an aim to reduce the time lag between technology generation and their transfer. The KVK was of national importance which would help in accelerating the agriculture production as also in improving the socio-economic conditions of the farming community and for providing self employment opportunities to the growing rural population. To achieve this objective the KVK arrange a number of training programs and activities on crop production and allied activities. The achievements of KVKs are measured in terms of impact of these trainings on the farming community. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the impact of KVK on level of knowledge, adoption and attitude towards various activities of KVK. With this task in view a study entitled, "Impact of Krushi Vigyan Kendra, Banaskantha-I on potato production technology" was be conducted with following specific objectives:

Objective

To study the impact of Krushi Vigyan Kendra on adoption level of potato growers about potato production technology

Methodology

The present study was undertaken in KVK at Deesa of Banaskantha district. Gujarat state has 33 districts, out of which Banaskantha district was selected for this study as Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Banaskantha-I (Deesa) is situated in this district. Banaskantha-I (Deesa), was first KVK in Gujarat state is established in 22nd February, 1976 in the 5th five years plan of the ICAR. This KVK was under Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University Jurisdiction. The study was confirmed to Ex-Post Facto research design. The multistage sampling technique was used for select a representative sample of respondents for present investigation. Out of 14 talukas of Banaskantha District Deesa, Dantiwada, Vadgam and Palanpur taluka was purposively selected on the basis of maximum numbers of activities carried out by KVK, Banaskantha-I (Deesa). From each selected talukas three villages were selected purposively on the basis of maximum numbers of beneficiary and more number of activities carried out by Krushi Vigyan Kendra, Banaskantha-I (Deesa). Thus, total twelve villages were selected. From the list of KVK beneficiary ten beneficiary potato growers from each village were selected randomly. To know the impact of KVK, the same numbers of non beneficiary potato growers were selected randomly from same villages. Thus, altogether

120 beneficiary and 120 non beneficiary potato growers were selected for the study. Thus, total 240 potato growers were selected. The data were collected by personal contact method with the help of structured interview schedule and collected data were coded, classified, tabulated and analyzed in light of objective and in order to make the findings meaningful for drawing meaningful interpretation. 'Z' test was applied to determine the difference between KVK beneficiary and non beneficiary potato growers for their adoption level.

Result And Discussion

Impact of Krushi Vigyan Kendra on adoption level of potato growers about potato production technology

New technology so far developed in recent past for boosting-up agricultural production and productivity is complex and hence, it requires proper assimilation by the consumers for adoption. Unless the technology is properly adopted to larger extent by the farmers, the desired targets can not be achieved. Efforts are made in this direction by the extension personnel for bringing down communication gap as well as making the farmers to understand the new technology finally adopting into practices. Farmers may adopt or reject new agricultural technology. Some farmers are aware of new agricultural technology and realize its importance. Hence, they adopt the technology to achieve higher yield for their betterment of life. Past studies have shown that farmers adopt the technology to its maximum limit and some of them adopt to its lower limit while some of the farmers adopt the technology at medium level.

The "Adoption Process" is the mental process through which an individual passes from first hearing about an innovation to its final adoption while, "Adoption" is a decision to continue full use of innovation. An attempt has also been made to find out extent of adoption of potato production technology by the beneficiary and non beneficiary farmers.

The main objectives in our agricultural strategies is to increase the total agriculture production as well as to puss the efficiency various input used by the rural community. The technologies that are developed at the agriculture research institute needs to be adopted by the vast majority of the farmers so that agriculture production is accelerated by efficient used input. The adoption of recommended technologies by the farmers is prime importance of the KVK. In order to ascertain adoption about improved agricultural technologies of potato crop, the respondent asked to give the account of package of practices they followed in potato cultivation. Adoption quotients of potato crop for each respondent calculated and they were classified in to three categories of adoptions viz., low, medium and high level adoption. The data presented in this regard in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of the potato growers according to their adoption level about potato production technology

Sr. No.	Adoption level	Beneficiary farmers			Non beneficiary farmers		
		Score	Frequency	Per cent	Score	Frequency	Per cent
1	Low	(< 14.02)	25	20.83	(< 11.30)	48	40.00
2	Medium	(≥14.02 to < 20.36)	67	55.84	(≥11.30 to < 17.28)	56	46.67
3	High	(≥ 20.36)	28	23.33	(≥17.28)	16	13.33
Total			120	100.00		120	100.00
Mean			17.19			14.29	
S.D.			3.16			2.98	
'Z' value			Calculated value: 4.45**				

It is evident from the data presented in Table 1 that more than half (55.84%) of beneficiary farmers had medium level of adoption of potato production technology, followed by 23.33 per cent and 20.83 per cent of them had high and low level of adoption of potato production technology, respectively. In case of non beneficiary farmers, (46.67%) of them had medium level of adoption of potato production technology, followed by 40.00 per cent and 13.33 per cent of them had low and high level of adoption of potato production technology, respectively.

It is evident from Table 1 that 'Z' value (4.45**) was found to be highly significant, which indicate that beneficiary potato growers had significantly higher adoption about potato production technology than non beneficiary potato growers, the significant difference in adoption level provide sufficient ground to reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}). The probable reason for having highly significant difference may be due to medium level of knowledge and that beneficiary potato growers remained in continuous touch with the extension personnel

throughout the session of the training so they might have acquired sufficient skills pertaining to potato cultivation practice.

These results were in congruence with Chaudhary (2018), Kakkad (2019), Chaudhary (2020) and Bora *et al.* (2022).

Practice-wise adoption of the potato growers about potato production technologies

The information regarding practice-wise adoption of the potato growers about potato production technologies is furnished in Table 2. In case of beneficiary farmers, practices-wise adoption level of the potato growers about potato production technology in descending order was: (I) preparation of land (89.58%), (II) improved varieties (87.50%), (III) planting time and method (85.41%), (IV) spacing (83.33%), (V) harvesting (78.33%), (VI) seed rate (75.00%), (VII) irrigation management (66.11%), (VIII) seed treatment (63.11%), (IX) post harvest management (61.66%), (X) nutrient management (54.16%), (XI) weed management (53.33%), (XII) plant protection measures (49.58%), (XIII) earthing-up (38.33%) and (XIV) crop rotation (36.66%).

Table 2: Practices-wise adoption of the potato growers about potato production technology

Sr. No.	Name of Practices	Maxi. score	Beneficiary farmers (n = 120)			Non beneficiary farmers (n = 120)		
			Obtained score	Per cent	Rank	Obtained score	Per cent	Rank
1	Preparation of land	240	215	89.58	I	184	76.66	I
2	Improved varieties	120	105	87.50	II	88	73.33	II
3	Seed rate	120	90	75.00	VI	68	56.66	VII
4	Seed treatment	240	152	63.33	VIII	130	54.16	VIII
5	Planting time and method	240	205	85.41	III	168	70.00	III
6	Spacing	120	100	83.33	IV	70	58.33	VI
7	Earthing-up	120	46	38.33	XIII	41	34.16	XIII
8	Nutrient management	480	260	54.16	X	220	45.83	X
9	Irrigation management	360	238	66.11	VII	216	60.27	V
10	Crop rotation	120	44	36.66	XIV	40	33.33	XIV
11	Weed management	240	128	53.33	XI	101	42.08	XI
12	Plant protection measures	480	238	49.58	XII	190	39.58	XII
13	Harvesting	120	94	78.33	V	76	63.33	IV
14	Post-harvest management	240	149	61.66	IX	122	50.83	IX

In case of non beneficiary farmers, practices-wise adoption level of the potato production technology in descending order was: (I) preparation of land (76.66%), (II) improved varieties (73.33%), (III) planting time and method (70.00%), (IV) harvesting (63.33%), (V) irrigation management (60.27%), (VI) spacing (58.33%), (VII) seed rate (56.66%), (VIII) seed treatment (54.16%), (IX) irrigation management (54.79%), (X) nutrient management (50.00%), (XI) weed management (42.08%), (XII) plant protection measures (39.58%), (XIII) earthing-up (34.16%) and (XIV) crop rotation (33.33%).

Conclusion

The finding of the study indicated that, majority (79.17%) of beneficiary farmers had medium to high level and 86.67 per cent of non beneficiary farmers had low to medium level of adoption of potato production technology. Reason might be due to sincere efforts put-forth by implementing agencies *i.e.* training by Krushi Vigyan Kendra to communicate the potato production technology to beneficiary potato growers. This may be perhaps due to positive impact of KVK's activities on beneficiary farmers in terms of increase in their knowledge, frequent extension contact, higher mass

media exposure and high social participation which may be resulted in their higher adoption of potato production technology.

Policy Implication

The result of the study concluded that some of the beneficiary and non beneficiary potato growers were not up to the expected level of adoption in terms of some of the areas of potato production technology. Hence, the extension efforts should be decided in best possible ways in developing an extension strategy to bring desired behavioral changes of adoption process.

Conflict Of Interest

The authors of the paper declare no conflict of interest

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